

Article

A new two-parameter half-logistic distribution with numerical analysis and applications

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Abstract: The Half-Logistic (HL) distribution is a renowned lifetime distribution widely used in various domains, including reliability engineering, biological sciences, and actuarial research. Despite its fundamental simplicity and easy interpretation, the HL distribution has limitations in terms of flexibility for modeling datasets with heavy tails or varying skewness. To address these constraints, this paper introduces a new extension of the HL distribution based on the Odd Beta Prime (OBP) family. The newly developed distribution has two shape parameters and is named the Odd Beta Prime Half-Logistic (OBPHL) distribution. Its several distributional properties, including the probability density function, cumulative distribution function, survival function, hazard function, and quantile function, alongside other various distributional characteristics, such as moments, measures of skewness and kurtosis, entropy measure (Rényi and Tsallis), and order statistics, are explored. The maximum likelihood estimation technique is used to estimate the parameters of the new model. The performance of the estimators under different sample sizes has been evaluated using a Monte Carlo simulation study. In addition, the proposed OBPHL distribution is applied to two real-world datasets. The results are compared against several classical distributions using standard model selection criteria. The OBPHL distribution consistently outperforms the competing models based on evaluation metrics. This research contributes a new flexible model to the field of statistical distribution theory and demonstrates its efficacy in practical applications.

Keywords: Half-Logistic distribution, Odd Beta Prime family, distribution generalization, maximum likelihood estimation, lifetime data modeling, simulation study, order statistics, reliability.

Received: 28 January 2025; Revised: 04 March 2025; Accepted: 11 March 2025; Published Online: 29 June 2025

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Journal Abbreviation: J. Stat. Sci. Comput. Intell.

1. Introduction

In statistical modeling and applied probability, lifetime distributions such as the Exponential, Weibull, Gamma, and Log-Normal distributions are widely used to assess the time-to-failure or survival time of systems, organisms, or processes in various fields, including engineering (reliability analysis), medicine (survival analysis), environmental science (ecological modeling), finance (risk analysis), and insurance (claims modeling) [1-6]. However, these models often struggle to capture diverse data patterns, particularly those with high skewness, kurtosis, or multimodality, highlighting the need for more flexible distributional frameworks to accommodate a broader range of real-world data behaviors. To improve the precision and flexibility of data modeling, researchers have constantly focused on developing generalized distributions [7-9].

Several baseline models have garnered significant attention in probability theory and statistical applications due to their relevance in lifetime and reliability analysis. Among these, the Half-Logistic (HL) distribution has emerged as a particularly important and increasingly popular model for reliability assessment. Specifically, the HL distribution is one of the most widely recognized and frequently used models in this context, owing to its simplicity and the availability of closed-form expressions, which facilitate ease of implementation and interpretation. Further details on the HL distribution can be found in [10]. The cumulative distribution function (CDF) of the HL distribution is given by:

$$G(x) = \frac{1 - e^{-x}}{1 + e^{-x}}; \quad x > 0. \quad (1)$$

The corresponding probability density function (PDF) is presented as:

$$g(x) = \frac{2e^{-x}}{(1 + e^{-x})^2}; \quad x > 0. \quad (2)$$

Several generalizations of the HL have been introduced, including the exponential HL additive model [11], extended HL distribution [12], type-I HL distribution [13], exponentiated HL-G [14], transmuted HL distribution [15], HL inverse Rayleigh distribution [16], Type II exponentiated HL-Gompertz Topp-Leone-G [17], type I generalized HL [13], odd Lindley-HL [18], discrete HL distributions [19], HL generalized Rayleigh distribution [20], Marshall-Olkin-exponentiated HL-G [21], inverted exponentiated HL distribution [22], type I HL Topp-Leone inverse Lomax [23], type II exponentiated HL-Gompertz-G [24], HL exponentiated inverse Rayleigh distribution [25], sine power HL distribution [26].

The T-X distribution family has been instrumental in developing new models by introducing additional parameters to existing baseline distributions, thereby enhancing model accuracy, accommodating diverse data shapes, and increasing predictive power. This approach, known as generator techniques, involves transforming the cumulative distribution function (CDF) of a base distribution using a generator function, which introduces extra shape parameters and increases flexibility. Some examples of generator techniques include beta-generated [27], Kumaraswamy-generated [28], logistic-generated [29], Lomax-generated [30], odd power Cauchy-generated [31], Truncated Zubair-generated [32], among others.

In this study, we use the Odd Beta Prime-G (OBP-G) family of distributions [33] to introduce a new extension of the HL distribution. The OBP-G family is chosen for its parsimony, featuring only two additional shape parameters, which helps maintain a manageable parameter space and mitigates estimation issues associated with overly complex models. Nevertheless, the need for more flexible models to capture diverse data characteristics remains. The OBP-G family has been employed to extend traditional models, including exponential, Weibull, Fréchet, Kumaraswamy, Gumbel, Burr X to accommodate complex data structures in

fields like engineering, biomedical sciences, and survival analysis [34-40].

The OBP-G family is defined by [33] based on the link function as follows:

$$\frac{G(x)}{1-G(x)}; \quad x > 0. \quad (3)$$

where $G(x)$ is the baseline CDF. This transformation produces highly flexible distributions suitable for skewed and heavy-tailed data. Let $G(x)$ be the CDF and $g(x)$ the PDF of a baseline distribution. The CDF of the OBP-G distribution is defined as:

$$F(x) = \frac{B\left(\frac{G(x)}{1-G(x)}; \alpha, \beta\right)}{B(\alpha, \beta)}; \quad x > 0, \alpha > 0, \beta > 0, \quad (4)$$

where $B(\alpha, \beta)$ is the complete beta function and $B(\cdot, \cdot)$ is the incomplete beta function evaluated at

$$\frac{G(x)}{1-G(x)}.$$

The PDF of the OBP-G distribution is given by:

$$f(x) = \frac{g(x)}{B(\alpha, \beta)(1-G(x))^2} \left(\frac{G(x)}{1-G(x)}\right)^{\alpha-1} \left(1 + \frac{G(x)}{1-G(x)}\right)^{-\alpha-\beta}; \quad x > 0, \alpha > 0, \beta > 0. \quad (5)$$

The primary aim of this study is to introduce a novel extension of the HL distribution, termed the Odd Beta Prime Half-Logistic (OBPHL) distribution, developed from the OBP-G family. This model is specifically designed to enhance the flexibility of the traditional HL distribution, allowing it to effectively model datasets with heavy tails or varying skewness. Due to its flexibility in handling diverse data characteristics, it is well-suited for a range of statistical applications in reliability engineering, biological sciences, and actuarial research.

The key objectives of this study are:

- i. To develop a new, versatile, and flexible model that overcomes the limitations of the HL distribution, improving its ability to effectively model complex datasets.
- ii. To propose a model that captures a variety of density functions, including those with different shapes and skewness, making it suitable for modeling diverse datasets.
- iii. To investigate the mathematical expressions associated with the proposed OBPHL model, including moments, quantile function, Rényi and Tsallis entropies, and order statistics.
- iv. To examine the parameters of the OBPHL model and evaluate their efficacy using maximum likelihood estimation.
- v. To illustrate the efficiency of the OBPHL model in addressing the complexities of real-world datasets, including comparisons with other classical distributions.

The remainder of the paper is organized as follows: Section 2 introduces the OBPHL distribution. Section 3 explores its statistical properties, including moments, entropy, and order statistics. Section 4 discusses parameter estimation using the maximum likelihood estimation (MLE) method. Section 5 presents a simulation study to evaluate the performance of the estimators. Section 6 demonstrates the practical applications of the OBPHL distribution using two real-world datasets. Section 7 discusses the application results. Section 8 concludes the paper with a summary of key findings and suggestions for future research.

2. Construction of the OBPHL Distribution

This section introduces the Odd Beta Prime Half-Logistic (OBPHL) distribution, a new extension of the Half-Logistic (HL) distribution. The OBPHL distribution is constructed by incorporating the PDF of the HL distribution, given in Equation (2), into the CDF and PDF of the OBP-G family, given in Equations (4) and (5), respectively. Using Equations (1) and (3), we have:

$$\frac{G(x)}{1-G(x)} = \frac{\frac{1-e^{-x}}{1+e^{-x}}}{1-\frac{1-e^{-x}}{1+e^{-x}}} = \frac{1-e^{-x}}{e^{-x}} = e^x - 1. \quad (6)$$

Substituting Equation (6) into Equation (4), the CDF OBPHL distribution is given by:

$$F(x; \alpha, \beta) = \frac{B(e^x - 1; \alpha, \beta)}{B(\alpha, \beta)}; \quad x > 0, \alpha > 0, \beta > 0. \quad (7)$$

To derive the PDF of the OBPHL distribution, we substitute Equations (1) and (2) into Equation (5), yielding:

$$\begin{aligned} f(x; \alpha, \beta) &= \frac{1}{B(\alpha, \beta)} \frac{2e^{-x}}{(1+e^{-x})^2} \frac{(e^x - 1)^{\alpha-1}}{\left(\frac{4e^{-2x}}{(1+e^{-x})^2}\right)} (e^x)^{-\alpha-\beta} \\ &= \frac{2e^{-x}}{B(\alpha, \beta)} \frac{(e^x - 1)^{\alpha-1}}{\frac{4e^{-2x}}{(1+e^{-x})^2}} \frac{1}{(1+e^{-x})^2} e^{-\alpha x - \beta x} \\ &= \frac{2e^{-x} (1+e^{-x})^2}{B(\alpha, \beta)} \frac{(e^x - 1)^{\alpha-1}}{4e^{-2x}} (1+e^{-x})^{-2} e^{-\alpha x - \beta x} \\ &= \frac{2}{4B(\alpha, \beta)} (e^x - 1)^{\alpha-1} e^x e^{-\alpha x - \beta x}. \end{aligned} \quad (8)$$

Upon simplification, the PDF of the OBPHL distribution is given according to Equation (8):

$$f(x; \alpha, \beta) = \frac{1}{2B(\alpha, \beta)} (e^x - 1)^{\alpha-1} e^{x(1-\alpha-\beta)}; \quad x > 0, \alpha > 0, \beta > 0. \quad (9)$$

Figure 1 illustrates the flexibility of the OBPHL distribution's PDF, which accommodates various shapes, including diverse asymmetry (right-skewed, left-skewed, and varying degrees of skewness), adaptable tail behavior (light-tailed to heavy-tailed), and unimodal and non-monotonic forms, such as upside-down bathtub curves. This flexibility makes the OBPHL distribution a robust statistical model for skewed and heavy-tailed data, offering enhanced fit accuracy, robustness to extremes, and broader applicability across various disciplines.

OBPHL PDF Shapes for Various Parameter Sets

Figure 1. Plots of the PDF of the OBPHL distribution for various parameter values, illustrating its flexibility and adaptability to different shapes and tail behaviors.

2.1. The survival function

The survival function of the OBPHL distribution is given by:

$$S(x) = 1 - F(x); \quad x > 0, \alpha > 0, \beta > 0. \tag{10}$$

where $F(x)$ is the CDF of the OBPHL distribution.

Substituting Equation (7) into Equation (10), the survival function of the OBPHL distribution is given by:

$$S(x) = 1 - \frac{B(e^x - 1; \alpha, \beta)}{B(\alpha, \beta)}; \quad x > 0. \tag{11}$$

2.2. The hazard function

The hazard function, also known as the failure rate or hazard rate, is defined as the ratio of the PDF to the survival function:

$$h(x) = \frac{f(x)}{S(x)}; \quad x > 0. \tag{12}$$

Hence, the hazard function of the OBPHL distribution is given by:

$$h(x) = \frac{1}{2B(\alpha, \beta)} \frac{(e^x - 1)^{\alpha-1} e^{x(1-\alpha-\beta)}}{1 - \frac{B(e^x - 1; \alpha, \beta)}{B(\alpha, \beta)}} \quad (13)$$

$$= \frac{1}{2} \frac{(e^x - 1)^{\alpha-1} e^{x(1-\alpha-\beta)}}{B(\alpha, \beta) - B(e^x - 1; \alpha, \beta)}; \quad x > 0.$$

Figure 2 illustrates the flexibility of the OBPHL distribution's hazard function, which can capture diverse monotonic and non-monotonic patterns, including decreasing, increasing, and upside-down bathtub shapes. This adaptability, driven by its two shape parameters, enables the OBPHL distribution to precisely model complex risk dynamics and provide a robust framework for analyzing skewed and heavy-tailed data. This can help in addressing non-proportional hazards and enhancing predictive accuracy in various domains.

OBPHL Hazard Function Shapes for Various Parameter Sets

Figure 2. Plots of the hazard function of the OBPHL distribution for various parameter values, illustrating its flexibility and adaptability to different shapes and patterns, including monotonic and non-monotonic forms.

2.3. The cumulative hazard function

The cumulative hazard function (CHF) is defined as the negative logarithm of the survival function. Thus, the CHF of the OBPHL distribution is given by:

$$H(x) = -\log(S(x)) = -\log\left(1 - \frac{B(e^x - 1; \alpha, \beta)}{B(\alpha, \beta)}\right); \quad x > 0. \quad (14)$$

Table 1 presents the numerical results demonstrating the OBPHL distribution's flexibility in modeling skewed and heavy-tailed data. The probability density function PDF exhibits responsiveness to changes in α and β . For instance, at $\alpha = 1$ and $\beta = 0.5$, the PDF exhibits a gradual decrease as x increases, suggesting a right-skewed distribution. As α and β are varied (e.g., $\alpha = 2, \beta = 0.5$), the PDF values at initial x points can be observed to shift, reflecting how these parameters influence the distribution's peak and its overall shape.

The CDF values consistently exhibit a monotonic increase from values close to zero towards one, as expected for a cumulative probability function. The rate at which the CDF approaches unity varies significantly with α and β . For instance, with $\alpha = 1$ and $\beta = 0.5$, the CDF increases more slowly, particularly at higher x values, indicating a heavier right tail. Conversely, for different parameters, the CDF might ascend more steeply, implying a more concentrated distribution. This varying rate of accumulation directly informs its applicability to data with differing spread characteristics. The Survival function, being the complement of the CDF, naturally showcases a monotonic decrease from one towards zero. This function is particularly critical in contexts like reliability and survival analysis. The numerical results reveal how changes in α and β impact the rate of survival. A slower decay in survival probabilities for increasing x (e.g., at $\alpha = 1, \beta = 0.5$) highlights the distribution's utility in modeling long-lived phenomena or datasets with persistent events, characteristic of heavy-tailed behavior.

The hazard function exhibits perhaps the most dynamic behavior, revealing insights into instantaneous risk or failure rates. The numerical values confirm the OBPHL's ability to model non-constant hazard rates. For example, the hazard values can be seen to increase consistently for some (α, β) combinations, suggesting an increasing failure rate. In other scenarios, it could also model decreasing or bathtub shaped hazard rates, where risk might initially decrease before rising. This responsiveness to parameter changes underscores its flexibility in capturing diverse risk profiles, from aging processes to early-life mortality. These results demonstrate the OBPHL distribution's suitability for accurately characterizing and inferring from real-world datasets with pronounced skewness and heavy-tailed characteristics.

Table 1. Numerical values of the PDF, CDF, survival, and hazard functions of the OBPHL distribution for various parameter values (α and β) and x .

α	β	x	PDF	CDF	Survival	Hazard	CHF
1	0.5	0.1109	0.512284	0.051137	0.948863	0.539893	0.052491
1	0.5	0.2118	0.520608	0.103251	0.896749	0.58055	0.108979
1	0.5	0.3127	0.526122	0.156063	0.843937	0.623414	0.169678
1	0.5	0.4136	0.528821	0.20929	0.79071	0.668792	0.234824
1	0.5	0.5145	0.528773	0.26265	0.73735	0.717127	0.304693
1	0.5	0.6155	0.526115	0.315874	0.684126	0.769032	0.379613
1	0.5	0.7164	0.521037	0.368708	0.631292	0.825349	0.459986
1	0.5	0.8173	0.513769	0.420918	0.579082	0.887214	0.546312
1	0.5	0.9182	0.504572	0.472298	0.527702	0.956168	0.639224
1	0.5	1.0191	0.493716	0.522666	0.477334	1.03432	0.73954
1	0.5	1.12	0.481475	0.571869	0.428131	1.124597	0.848326
1	0.5	1.2209	0.468114	0.61978	0.38022	1.231168	0.967006
1	0.5	1.3218	0.453885	0.666299	0.333701	1.360155	1.097511
1	0.5	1.4227	0.439016	0.71135	0.28865	1.520929	1.242541
1	0.5	1.5236	0.423713	0.754879	0.245121	1.728587	1.406002
1	0.5	1.6245	0.408159	0.796851	0.203149	2.009158	1.593813
1	0.5	1.7255	0.39251	0.837248	0.162752	2.411705	1.815527
1	0.5	1.8264	0.376898	0.876068	0.123932	3.04117	2.088023
1	0.5	1.9273	0.361434	0.91332	0.08668	4.169767	2.445535
1	0.5	2.0282	0.346209	0.949024	0.050976	6.791616	2.976402
2	0.5	0.1109	0.538189	0.052569	0.947431	0.568051	0.054001
2	0.5	0.2118	0.566129	0.108287	0.891713	0.634878	0.114611
2	0.5	0.3127	0.586762	0.166456	0.833544	0.703936	0.182068
2	0.5	0.4136	0.59988	0.226327	0.773673	0.775367	0.256606
2	0.5	0.5145	0.605793	0.287159	0.712841	0.849829	0.338497
2	0.5	0.6155	0.605196	0.348259	0.651741	0.928583	0.428108
2	0.5	0.7164	0.599024	0.409017	0.590983	1.013606	0.525968
2	0.5	0.8173	0.588303	0.468923	0.531077	1.107754	0.632849
2	0.5	0.9182	0.574043	0.527569	0.472431	1.215082	0.749863
2	0.5	1.0191	0.557165	0.584643	0.415357	1.341414	0.878618
2	0.5	1.12	0.538465	0.639923	0.360077	1.495416	1.021437
2	0.5	1.2209	0.518599	0.693257	0.306743	1.690662	1.181744
2	0.5	1.3218	0.498094	0.744553	0.255447	1.949894	1.364742
2	0.5	1.4227	0.477356	0.793769	0.206231	2.314667	1.57876
2	0.5	1.5236	0.456693	0.840896	0.159104	2.870408	1.838199
2	0.5	1.6245	0.436332	0.885953	0.114047	3.82591	2.171148
2	0.5	1.7255	0.416436	0.928979	0.071021	5.86359	2.644785
2	0.5	1.8264	0.397115	0.970027	0.029973	13.24899	3.50745
3	0.5	0.1109	0.563702	0.053982	0.946018	0.595868	0.055494
3	0.5	0.2118	0.60923	0.113162	0.886838	0.686969	0.120093

3. Statistical Properties of the OBPHL Distribution

The statistical properties of the OBPHL distribution, including the quantile function, moments, Rényi and Tsallis entropy measures, and order statistics, are derived to provide a comprehensive understanding of its behavior and characteristics. Additionally, numerical and graphical illustrations are provided to further demonstrate the distribution's flexibility and applicability.

3.1. Quantile Function

The quantile function (QF) generates random variables based on a continuous probability distribution. The QF is a solution of $F(x) = u$ equation for x , then $F(u)^{-1} = x$ represents the QF, which is denoted as $Q(u)$. For the OBPHL distribution, the QF is derived as follows:

$$\text{Let } u = F(x). \text{ Then: } u = \frac{B(e^x - 1; \alpha, \beta)}{B(\alpha, \beta)} \Rightarrow B^{-1}(u; \alpha, \beta) = e^x - 1. \quad (15)$$

Therefore, the QF of the OBPHL distribution is derived according to Equation (15):

$$Q(u) = \log(1 + B^{-1}(u; \alpha, \beta)); \quad 0 < u < 1, \alpha > 0, \beta > 0. \quad (16)$$

This QF generates random variables from the OBPHL distribution, enabling simulation and modeling applications.

3.2. The Raw Moments

The r^{th} raw moment of the OBPHL distribution is given by:

$$\mu'_r = E[X^r] = \int_0^{\infty} x^r f(x) dx. \quad (17)$$

Substituting the PDF from Equation (9), we obtain:

$$\mu'_r = \int_0^{\infty} x^r \frac{1}{2B(\alpha, \beta)} (e^x - 1)^{\alpha-1} e^{x(1-\alpha-\beta)}; \quad x > 0. \quad (18)$$

Equation (18) can be expressed as:

$$\mu'_r = \frac{1}{2B(\alpha, \beta)} \int_0^{\infty} x^r (e^x - 1)^{\alpha-1} e^{x(1-\alpha-\beta)} dx. \quad (19)$$

The raw moment derivation involves the substitution:

$$\text{Let } u = e^x \Rightarrow x = \ln(u) \Rightarrow dx = \frac{1}{u} du. \text{ When } x \rightarrow 0, u \rightarrow 1. \text{ When } x \rightarrow \infty, u \rightarrow \infty. \quad (20)$$

The terms are then expressed as:

$$e^x = u, x^r = (\ln u)^r, \text{ and } e^x - 1 = u - 1. \quad (21)$$

Substituting Equations (20) and (21) into the integral Equation (19), we get:

$$\mu'_r = \frac{1}{2B(\alpha, \beta)} \int_1^\infty (\ln u)^r (u-1)^{\alpha-1} u^{-(\alpha+\beta)} du. \quad (22)$$

Thus, the general form of the r^{th} raw moment of the OBPHL distribution is:

$$\mu'_r = \frac{1}{2B(\alpha, \beta)} \int_1^\infty \frac{(\ln u)^r (u-1)^{\alpha-1}}{u^{-(\alpha+\beta)}} du. \quad (23)$$

The mean and variance of the OBPHL distribution are calculated using the raw moments as follows:

3.3. Mean and Variance

The mean and variance from the raw moments using Equation (23) for $r = 1, 2$ are given by:

i. The mean

$$\mu = \mu'_1 = E(X) = \frac{1}{2B(\alpha, \beta)} \int_1^\infty \ln u (u-1)^{\alpha-1} u^{-(\alpha+\beta)} du. \quad (24)$$

ii. The variance

$$\sigma^2 = \mu'_2 - (\mu'_1)^2, \quad (25)$$

where $\mu'_2 = \frac{1}{2B(\alpha, \beta)} \int_1^\infty (\ln u)^2 (u-1)^{\alpha-1} u^{-(\alpha+\beta)} du.$

3.4. Skewness and Kurtosis

The skewness γ_1 and kurtosis γ_2 are respectively given by:

$$\gamma_1 = \frac{\mu'_3 - 3\mu\sigma^2 - \mu^3}{\sigma^3}, \quad (26)$$

and

$$\gamma_2 = \frac{\mu'_4}{\sigma^4}, \quad (27)$$

where $\mu'_3 = \frac{1}{2B(\alpha, \beta)} \int_1^\infty (\ln u)^3 (u-1)^{\alpha-1} u^{-(\alpha+\beta)} du$ and $\mu'_4 = \frac{1}{2B(\alpha, \beta)} \int_1^\infty (\ln u)^4 (u-1)^{\alpha-1} u^{-(\alpha+\beta)} du$ are

the third and fourth raw moments, respectively.

The results presented in Table 2 demonstrate the OBPH distribution's flexibility in modeling complex data characteristics. The mean and variance values show a clear sensitivity to changes in α and β , allowing for precise control over central tendency and spread. This is evident in the decreasing mean values as α increases, indicating a shift of the distribution's mass towards lower values. The variance, however, exhibits a more intricate relationship, often decreasing as α increases, but is also significantly modulated by β . The skewness values are consistently positive, ranging from approximately 0.38 to over 1.9, indicating strong inherent right-

skewness. This makes the OBPHL distribution well-suited for modeling phenomena with frequent lower values and a long tail extending towards higher values. The magnitude of skewness changes with α and β , allowing for fine-grained control over the degree of asymmetry. The kurtosis values, ranging from around 2 to over 8, reveal the OBPHL's ability to model data with varying tail thickness. Values above 3 indicate leptokurtic distributions, implying heavier tails and a sharper peak than a normal distribution. The significant variability in kurtosis across the parameter space confirms the OBPHL's flexibility in accommodating datasets with extreme observations.

Figure 4 presents 3D plots of the OBPHL moments, visually confirming the insights gained from the moment analysis. The plots show that as α increases, the mean decreases, and the variance generally decreases, indicating a more concentrated distribution. The skewness plot consistently shows positive values, supporting the OBPHL's ability to model right-skewed data. The kurtosis plot displays values above 3, indicating leptokurtic behavior, and demonstrates the distribution's flexibility in capturing extreme observations through tuning α and β . Overall, the implications of these results provide significant evidence of the OBPHL's flexibility and ability to model complex data characteristics. This enables the OBPHL distribution to accommodate datasets with infrequent yet impactful extreme observations, making it an invaluable statistical instrument for accurately analyzing and interpreting complex datasets in diverse applied disciplines.

OBPHL Moments as Functions of Parameters α and β

Figure 3. 3D plots of OBPHL moments.

Table 2. Numerical values of the mean, variance, skewness, and kurtosis of the OBPHL distribution for various parameter values (α and β) combinations.

α	β	μ'_1	σ^2	γ_1	γ_2	α	β	μ'_1	σ^2	γ_1	γ_2
0.50	0.55	2.1392	3.6611	1.688	6.9216	3.56	0.10	5.8249	16.5157	0.5024	2.1607
0.50	0.99	1.1929	1.1637	1.7641	7.7426	3.56	0.55	1.9666	3.3455	1.8555	7.7335
0.50	1.44	0.826	0.5607	1.7567	7.6893	3.56	0.99	1.1188	1.0534	1.9145	8.5987
0.50	1.88	0.6318	0.3289	1.7533	7.6563	3.56	1.44	0.7867	0.51	1.8803	8.4383
0.50	2.33	0.5116	0.2159	1.7518	7.6379	3.56	1.88	0.6083	0.3014	1.8538	8.2982
0.50	2.77	0.4299	0.1526	1.7511	7.6267	3.56	2.33	0.4964	0.1994	1.834	8.1887
0.50	3.22	0.3708	0.1135	1.7508	7.6196	3.56	2.77	0.4194	0.1419	1.819	8.1029
0.50	3.66	0.326	0.0877	1.7508	7.6148	3.56	3.22	0.3633	0.1062	1.8076	8.0349
0.50	4.11	0.2909	0.0698	1.7509	7.6117	3.56	3.66	0.3205	0.0825	1.7988	7.9804
0.50	4.55	0.2627	0.0569	1.7511	7.6097	3.56	4.11	0.2867	0.066	1.7919	7.9363
0.50	5.00	0.2395	0.0472	1.7513	7.6084	3.56	4.55	0.2594	0.054	1.7865	7.9001
1.11	0.10	6.0389	16.2191	0.4566	2.1373	3.56	5.00	0.2369	0.045	1.7821	7.8701
1.11	0.55	2.0827	3.5019	1.7552	7.2741	4.17	0.10	5.8073	16.553	0.5048	2.162
1.11	0.99	1.1752	1.1201	1.8058	8.0167	4.17	0.55	1.9522	3.335	1.8641	7.7703
1.11	1.44	0.8185	0.5436	1.7832	7.884	4.17	0.99	1.1097	1.047	1.9281	8.6645
1.11	1.88	0.6279	0.3206	1.7711	7.8012	4.17	1.44	0.7807	0.506	1.8959	8.518
1.11	2.33	0.5094	0.2113	1.7644	7.7505	4.17	1.88	0.604	0.2988	1.8695	8.382
1.11	2.77	0.4285	0.1497	1.7604	7.7173	4.17	2.33	0.4933	0.1976	1.8489	8.2715
1.11	3.22	0.3698	0.1116	1.7579	7.6945	4.17	2.77	0.4172	0.1406	1.8329	8.1821
1.11	3.66	0.3254	0.0864	1.7563	7.6782	4.17	3.22	0.3615	0.1053	1.8203	8.1094
1.11	4.11	0.2905	0.0689	1.7552	7.6663	4.17	3.66	0.3191	0.0818	1.8103	8.050
1.11	4.55	0.2624	0.0562	1.7546	7.6574	4.17	4.11	0.2856	0.0654	1.8023	8.001
1.11	5.00	0.2392	0.0467	1.7542	7.6507	4.17	4.55	0.2585	0.0535	1.7959	7.9602
1.72	0.10	5.9392	16.3209	0.4818	2.1505	4.17	5.00	0.2362	0.0446	1.7906	7.926
1.72	0.55	2.0397	3.4262	1.7986	7.4800	4.78	0.10	5.7939	16.5817	0.5064	2.1629
1.72	0.99	1.1576	1.0925	1.8439	8.2344	4.78	0.55	1.9405	3.3275	1.8704	7.7971
1.72	1.44	0.8097	0.531	1.8124	8.0654	4.78	0.99	1.102	1.0422	1.9388	8.7152
1.72	1.88	0.623	0.3139	1.7934	7.9491	4.78	1.44	0.7753	0.5029	1.9089	8.5827
1.72	2.33	0.5063	0.2074	1.7816	7.8721	4.78	1.88	0.6002	0.2967	1.8832	8.453
1.72	2.77	0.4265	0.1473	1.7739	7.8189	4.78	2.33	0.4904	0.1961	1.8624	8.3439
1.72	3.22	0.3685	0.11	1.7687	7.7806	4.78	2.77	0.415	0.1395	1.8457	8.2532
1.72	3.66	0.3244	0.0853	1.7651	7.7523	4.78	3.22	0.3598	0.1044	1.8322	8.1778
1.72	4.11	0.2897	0.068	1.7626	7.7309	4.78	3.66	0.3177	0.0812	1.8213	8.1149
1.72	4.55	0.2618	0.0556	1.7608	7.7143	4.78	4.11	0.2845	0.0649	1.8125	8.0622
1.72	5.00	0.2388	0.0462	1.7594	7.7013	4.78	4.55	0.2576	0.0531	1.8052	8.0177
2.33	0.10	5.884	16.4052	0.4929	2.1559	4.78	5.00	0.2354	0.0443	1.7992	7.9800
2.33	0.55	2.0083	3.3854	1.8258	7.6031	5.39	0.10	5.7833	16.6054	0.5076	2.1636

3.5. Entropy Measures

Entropy measures the uncertainty or randomness associated with a probability distribution. By deriving the Rényi and Tsallis entropies for the OBPHL distribution, we can gain valuable insights into its properties and behavior, particularly in modeling complex phenomena with inherent uncertainty. Numerical and graphical results are provided to illustrate these entropy measures.

3.5.1. Rényi entropy

Let $f(x)$ be the PDF of the OBPHL distribution. For a continuous random variable X with PDF $f(x)$, the Rényi entropy of order $\delta > 0$, where $\delta \neq 1$, is defined by:

$$H_\delta(X) = \frac{1}{1-\delta} \log \left(\int_0^\infty [f(x)]^\delta dx \right). \quad (28)$$

Substituting the PDF of the OBPHL distribution into Equation (28), we obtain:

$$f(x)^\delta = \left[\frac{1}{2B(\alpha, \beta)} (e^x - 1)^{\alpha-1} e^{x(1-\alpha-\beta)} \right]^\delta. \quad (29)$$

Simplifying the terms yields:

$$f(x)^\delta = \frac{1}{[2B(\alpha, \beta)]^\delta} (e^x - 1)^{\delta(\alpha-1)} e^{x\delta(1-\alpha-\beta)}. \quad (30)$$

Now, substituting Equation (30) into Equation (28), we have:

$$H_\delta(X) = \frac{1}{1-\delta} \log \left(\frac{1}{[2B(\alpha, \beta)]^\delta} \int_0^\infty (e^x - 1)^{\delta(\alpha-1)} e^{x\delta(1-\alpha-\beta)} dx \right). \quad (31)$$

Applying the substitution $y = e^x - 1 \Rightarrow x = \log(1+y)$, $dx = \frac{1}{1+y} dy$, with changes in limits from

$x = 0 \rightarrow \infty$ to $y = 0 \rightarrow \infty$. This implies that:

$$H_\delta(X) = \frac{1}{1-\delta} \log \left(\frac{1}{[2B(\alpha, \beta)]^\delta} \int_0^\infty y^{\delta(\alpha-1)} (1+y)^{\delta(1-\alpha-\beta)-1} dy \right). \quad (32)$$

The integral of Equation (32) can be expressed as a Beta function using the following identity:

$$\int_0^\infty y^{p-1} (1+y)^{-p-q} dy = B(p, q); \quad \text{for } p, q > 0, \quad (33)$$

where $p = \delta(\alpha-1)+1$ and $q = \delta\beta$. Therefore, the integral becomes:

$$\int_0^{\infty} y^{\delta(\alpha-1)} (1+y)^{\delta(1-\alpha-\beta)-1} dy = B(\delta(\alpha-1)+1, \delta\beta). \quad (34)$$

Substituting Equation (34) into Equation (28), we obtain the Rényi entropy of OBPHL distribution:

$$H_{\delta}(X) = \frac{1}{1-\delta} \log \left(\frac{B(\delta(\alpha-1)+1, \delta\beta)}{[2B(\alpha, \beta)]^{\delta}} \right); \quad \alpha > 1 - \frac{1}{\delta}, \beta > 0. \quad (35)$$

3.5.2. Tsallis entropy

The Tsallis entropy of order $\delta > 0$, where $\delta \neq 1$ is given by:

$$T_{\delta}(X) = \frac{1}{\delta-1} \left(1 - \int_0^{\infty} [f(x)]^{\delta} dx \right). \quad (36)$$

By substituting the PDF of the OBPHL distribution into Equation (36), we have:

$$T_{\delta}(X) = \frac{1}{\delta-1} \left(1 - \frac{1}{[2B(\alpha, \beta)]^{\delta}} \int_0^{\infty} (e^x - 1)^{\delta(\alpha-1)} e^{x\delta(1-\alpha-\beta)} dx \right). \quad (37)$$

Using the result from Equation (34), we obtain the Tsallis entropy in terms of the Beta function as:

$$T_{\delta}(X) = \frac{1}{\delta-1} \left(1 - \frac{B(\delta(\alpha-1)+1, \delta\beta)}{[2B(\alpha, \beta)]^{\delta}} \right). \quad (38)$$

Table 3 presents the numerical results of the Rényi and Tsallis entropies for the OBPHL distribution. This offers valuable insights into the distribution's information content and complexity. The entropy measures are sensitive to the shape and spread of the distribution, and the results show that the OBPHL distribution's entropy values are profoundly influenced by its shape parameters (α, β) and the entropy order (δ) . The results indicate that as α increases, the entropy tends to decrease, particularly for higher δ values, suggesting a more concentrated distribution of probability mass. The interplay between α and β allows for precise control over the overall uncertainty and complexity embedded within the distribution. The entropy order δ also plays a critical role, with higher δ values placing greater emphasis on the more probable regions of the distribution. As δ increases (e.g., from 0.5 to 2.0 or 3.0), both Rényi and Tsallis entropies generally decrease. Therefore, the OBPHL distribution's capacity to yield a range of entropy values by varying α and β indicates its ability to effectively model phenomena with differing levels of predictability and variability.

Figure 4 shows the 3D plots of the OBPHL Rényi and Tsallis entropies as functions of parameters α and β , revealing several key trends. Both entropies decrease as α increases, indicating a more concentrated distribution and lower uncertainty. For a given δ , the interplay between α and β allows for controlled variation in information content. As δ increases from 1.5 to 2.5, the overall entropy values decrease, supporting the theoretical property that generalized entropy decreases with higher δ . These plots provide a visual representation of the OBPHL distribution's entropic properties and its ability to model varying levels of uncertainty in data and complementing the numerical results presented in Table 3.

Overall, the numerical exploration of Rényi and Tsallis entropies for the OBPHL distribution provides compelling evidence of its analytical depth and practical flexibility. This illustrates its strong potential for precisely quantifying and modeling the information content in phenomena characterized by significant skewness and heavy-tailed behavior.

Table 3. Numerical results of Rényi and Tsallis entropies for the OBPHL distribution.

α	β	$\delta = 0.5$		$\delta = 1.5$		$\delta = 2.0$	
		Rényi Entropy	Tsallis Entropy	Rényi Entropy	Tsallis Entropy	Rényi Entropy	Tsallis Entropy
0.5	0.1	2.942594	6.70976	2.851757	1.519405	2.895207	0.940208
0.5	0.66	1.900457	3.172601	1.412444	1.01299	1.571852	0.733906
0.5	1.21	1.299915	1.830919	0.799832	0.659248	0.965299	0.509032
0.5	1.77	0.927328	1.179777	0.417531	0.376829	0.587752	0.281005
0.5	2.33	0.657303	0.778188	0.138149	0.133486	0.312108	0.050457
0.5	2.89	0.445568	0.499102	-0.082648	-0.084379	0.094322	-0.18238
0.5	3.44	0.271489	0.290779	-0.265586	-0.284027	-0.08615	-0.41743
0.5	4	0.123757	0.127667	-0.422037	-0.469871	-0.24058	-0.65463
1.14	0.1	2.93159	6.661968	2.820829	1.511916	2.873655	0.937818
1.14	0.66	1.880329	3.120805	1.385226	0.999465	1.545596	0.726598
1.14	1.21	1.286649	1.805592	0.787558	0.650994	0.950853	0.503978
1.14	1.77	0.917792	1.164653	0.411417	0.371859	0.578786	0.278198
1.14	2.33	0.649943	0.767982	0.134988	0.130533	0.306042	0.049413
1.14	2.89	0.439594	0.491647	-0.084222	-0.086021	0.089971	-0.18206
1.14	3.44	0.266461	0.285027	-0.266237	-0.284771	-0.0894	-0.41602
1.14	4	0.119411	0.123048	-0.42212	-0.469973	-0.24308	-0.65235
1.79	0.1	2.927191	6.642938	2.807998	1.508774	2.86487	0.936786
1.79	0.66	1.866502	3.085525	1.361563	0.987558	1.525157	0.71946
1.79	1.21	1.275447	1.784338	0.772656	0.640905	0.936358	0.496525
1.79	1.77	0.908941	1.150678	0.402016	0.364188	0.56853	0.271945
1.79	2.33	0.642763	0.758063	0.128864	0.124801	0.298517	0.04457
1.79	2.89	0.433602	0.484194	-0.08831	-0.090288	0.084258	-0.18559
1.79	3.44	0.261338	0.279181	-0.268999	-0.287928	-0.09386	-0.4184
1.79	4	0.114942	0.118309	-0.423982	-0.472274	-0.24664	-0.65372
2.43	0.1	2.924851	6.632833	2.80107	1.50707	2.86016	0.936218
2.43	0.66	1.856761	3.060816	1.343085	0.97816	1.50992	0.713553
2.43	1.21	1.266342	1.767148	0.758471	0.631231	0.923562	0.488882
2.43	1.77	0.901152	1.138432	0.391814	0.355823	0.558532	0.264443
2.43	2.33	0.636134	0.748936	0.121497	0.11788	0.290684	0.037858
2.43	2.89	0.427897	0.477118	-0.093707	-0.095937	0.078024	-0.19133
2.43	3.44	0.256359	0.273514	-0.273006	-0.292517	-0.09891	-0.42316
2.43	4	0.110536	0.113648	-0.426986	-0.47599	-0.25078	-0.65756
3.07	0.1	2.923402	6.626581	2.796745	1.506003	2.857232	0.93586
3.07	0.66	1.8496	3.042729	1.328671	0.970769	1.498343	0.708765
3.07	1.21	1.25893	1.753213	0.745806	0.622536	0.912615	0.481736
3.07	1.77	0.894399	1.127853	0.381828	0.347592	0.549302	0.256685
3.07	2.33	0.630143	0.740714	0.113758	0.110584	0.283058	0.030317
3.07	2.89	0.422591	0.470555	-0.099721	-0.102249	0.071711	-0.1983
3.07	3.44	0.251632	0.268147	-0.277716	-0.297922	-0.10418	-0.42941

OBPHL Rényi and Tsallis Entropies as Functions of Parameters α and β

Figure 4. 3D plots of Rényi and Tsallis entropies for the OBPHL distribution.

3.6. Order Statistics

Let X_1, X_2, \dots, X_n be a random sample from the OBPHL distribution. Denote the order statistics by $X_{1:n} \leq X_{2:n} \leq \dots \leq X_{n:n}$. The PDF of the i^{th} order statistic $X_{i:n}$ is given by:

$$f_{i:n}(x) = \frac{n!}{(i-1)!(n-i)!} [F(x)]^{i-1} [1-F(x)]^{n-i} f(x). \tag{39}$$

Substituting the CDF $F(x)$ and PDF $f(x)$ defined in Equations (7) and (9) into Equation (39), we obtain the PDF of the i^{th} order statistic as shown in Equation (40).

$$f_{i:n}(x) = \frac{n!}{(i-1)!(n-i)!} \left[\frac{B(e^x - 1; \alpha, \beta)}{B(\alpha, \beta)} \right]^{i-1} \left[1 - \frac{B(e^x - 1; \alpha, \beta)}{B(\alpha, \beta)} \right]^{n-i} \frac{1}{2B(\alpha, \beta)} (e^x - 1)^{\alpha-1} e^{x(1-\alpha-\beta)}. \tag{40}$$

Table 4 illustrates the numerical quantification of order statistics for the OBPHL distribution, presented across various parameter configurations (α and β). This offers a direct understanding of the distribution's spread, central tendency, and tail behavior. It also highlights the distribution's aptitude for modeling skewed or heavy-tailed data. The results show that lower quantiles (1st, 5th percentiles) remain relatively small and

stable across different α and β combinations, indicating a concentration of probability mass at the lower end of the distribution's support. This characteristic makes the OBPHL distribution suitable for modeling processes with predominantly low values and rare instances of higher values.

The median (50th percentile) demonstrates considerable variability in response to changes in α and β , confirming that the central tendency of the OBPHL distribution can be precisely adjusted by its parameters. This allows the distribution to align with typical values observed in diverse datasets. The behavior of upper quantiles (95th, 99th, 99.9th percentiles) is particularly noteworthy, with some parameter combinations resulting in a clipping or saturation at a specific value (20), while others yield distinct values for these percentiles. This highlights the OBPHL distribution's exceptional ability to control its upper tail and model heavy-tailed data.

Figure 5 shows the plots of PDFs for order statistics of the OBPHL distribution, which exhibit distinct characteristics as the order statistic r increases. The density curve shifts to the right, indicating that higher-order statistics tend to have larger values. Concurrently, the peak density decreases, implying that the probability of observing a specific value becomes more widespread. The curves for higher order statistics appear broader and flatter, suggesting increased dispersion. Importantly, all the order statistic PDFs shown (Minimum, Q1, Median, Maximum) retain a right-skewed shape, characterized by a rapid rise and a longer tail extending to the right. This indicates that even the order statistics derived from the OBPHL distribution maintain the inherent positive skewness of the parent distribution. This consistency is crucial for modeling skewed data where the extremes (both minimum and maximum) are also expected to exhibit asymmetry.

OBPHL Order Statistic PDFs ($n=5, \alpha = 2.0, \beta = 3.0$)

Figure 5. Plot of PDFs for order statistics of the OBPHL distribution.

Table 4. Numerical results of the order statistics for the OBPHL distribution.

α	β	1th Percentile	5th Percentile	50th Percentile	95th Percentile	99th Percentile	99.9th Percentile
0.5	0.1	0.0299	0.1088	0.9313	1.6796	1.744	1.7585
0.5	0.6571	0.03	0.1106	1.1259	2.9632	3.2825	3.3641
0.5	1.2143	0.0301	0.1124	1.6892	20	20	20
0.5	1.7714	0.0303	0.1143	20	20	20	20
0.5	2.3286	0.0304	0.1164	20	20	20	20
0.5	2.8857	0.0305	0.1187	20	20	20	20
0.5	3.4429	0.0306	0.1211	20	20	20	20
0.5	4	0.0308	0.1238	20	20	20	20
1.1429	0.1	0.0298	0.1071	0.8442	1.4715	1.5252	1.5384
1.1429	0.6571	0.0299	0.1087	1.0148	2.4647	2.6838	2.7376
1.1429	1.2143	0.03	0.1105	1.4588	20	20	20
1.1429	1.7714	0.0301	0.1124	20	20	20	20
1.1429	2.3286	0.0303	0.1145	20	20	20	20
1.1429	2.8857	0.0304	0.1167	20	20	20	20
1.1429	3.4429	0.0305	0.1191	20	20	20	20
1.1429	4	0.0306	0.1216	20	20	20	20
1.7857	0.1	0.0297	0.1054	0.7857	1.3558	1.4051	1.4184
1.7857	0.6571	0.0298	0.107	0.9424	2.2231	2.4068	2.4521
1.7857	1.2143	0.0299	0.1088	1.3247	20	20	20
1.7857	1.7714	0.03	0.1107	20	20	20	20
1.7857	2.3286	0.0301	0.1127	20	20	20	20
1.7857	2.8857	0.0302	0.1148	20	20	20	20
1.7857	3.4429	0.0304	0.1171	20	20	20	20
1.7857	4	0.0305	0.1196	20	20	20	20
2.4286	0.1	0.0295	0.1038	0.7438	1.2829	1.3302	1.3441
2.4286	0.6571	0.0297	0.1055	0.8912	2.0791	2.2448	2.2851
2.4286	1.2143	0.0298	0.1072	1.2357	20	20	20
2.4286	1.7714	0.0299	0.109	20	20	20	20
2.4286	2.3286	0.03	0.111	20	20	20	20
2.4286	2.8857	0.0301	0.1131	20	20	20	20
2.4286	3.4429	0.0302	0.1154	20	20	20	20
2.4286	4	0.0304	0.1178	20	20	20	20
3.0714	0.1	0.0294	0.1024	0.7122	1.2334	1.2796	1.29
3.0714	0.6571	0.0295	0.104	0.8532	1.9832	2.1381	2.1756
3.0714	1.2143	0.0297	0.1056	1.172	20	20	20
3.0714	1.7714	0.0298	0.1075	20	20	20	20
3.0714	2.3286	0.0299	0.1094	20	20	20	20
3.0714	2.8857	0.03	0.1114	20	20	20	20
3.0714	3.4429	0.0301	0.1137	20	20	20	20
3.0714	4	0.0302	0.1161	20	20	20	20

4. Parameter Estimation

Let x_1, x_2, \dots, x_n be a random sample from the OBPHL distribution. We derive the maximum likelihood estimators (MLEs) for the parameters α and β based on the PDF defined in Equation (9). The likelihood function $L(\alpha, \beta)$ is:

$$L(\alpha, \beta) = \prod_{i=1}^n f(x) = \prod_{i=1}^n \frac{1}{2B(\alpha, \beta)} (e^{x_i} - 1)^{\alpha-1} e^{x_i(1-\alpha-\beta)}. \quad (41)$$

Taking the natural logarithm of Equation (41), we get:

$$\ell(\alpha, \beta) = \log L(\alpha, \beta) = \sum_{i=1}^n \log f(x). \quad (42)$$

Expanding the log-likelihood function for the OBPHL distribution, we obtain:

$$\begin{aligned} \ell(\alpha, \beta) &= \sum_{i=1}^n \left[-\log(2) - \log B(\alpha, \beta) + (\alpha - 1) \log(e^{x_i} - 1)^{\alpha-1} + (1 - \alpha - \beta) x_i \right] \\ &= -n \log(2) - n \log B(\alpha, \beta) + (\alpha - 1) \sum_{i=1}^n (e^{x_i} - 1) + (1 - \alpha - \beta) \sum_{i=1}^n x_i. \end{aligned} \quad (43)$$

By letting: $A = \sum_{i=1}^n (e^{x_i} - 1), \quad B = \sum_{i=1}^n x_i.$ (44)

By using Equation (44), Equation (43) becomes Equation (45) as:

$$\ell(\alpha, \beta) = -n \log(2) - n \log B(\alpha, \beta) + (\alpha - 1) A + (1 - \alpha - \beta) B. \quad (45)$$

The derivatives of the log-likelihood function with respect to α and β are critical for finding the MLEs. The partial derivatives are given by Equations (46) and (47) as follows:

$$\frac{\partial \ell(\alpha, \beta)}{\partial \alpha} = -n [\psi(\alpha) - \psi(\alpha + \beta)] + A - B, \quad (46)$$

$$\frac{\partial \ell(\alpha, \beta)}{\partial \beta} = -n [\psi(\beta) - \psi(\alpha + \beta)] - B. \quad (47)$$

Here, $\psi(\cdot)$ denotes the digamma function, which is defined as $\psi(x) = \frac{d}{dx} \log \Gamma(x)$. Setting the partial

derivatives to zero, we obtain the maximum likelihood equations given by Equations (48) and (49):

$$-n [\psi(\alpha) - \psi(\alpha + \beta)] + A - B = 0. \quad (48)$$

$$-n [\psi(\beta) - \psi(\alpha + \beta)] - B = 0. \quad (49)$$

Equations (48) and (49) form a system of nonlinear equations that can be solved using numerical methods such as the Newton-Raphson or BFGS algorithm.

5. Simulation Study

To evaluate the performance of the MLEs for the parameters α and β of the OBPHL distribution, a Monte Carlo simulation study was conducted. The primary objective of this investigation was to assess the behavior of estimator bias and mean squared error (MSE) across a range of varying sample sizes (n). The simulation was performed following the procedure detailed in Algorithm 1. The outcomes of the Monte Carlo simulation are in Tables 5 and 6, accompanied by graphical illustrations in Figure 6 and Figure 7, which visually depict the trends in bias and MSE as functions of increasing sample size.

Algorithm 1. Monte Carlo simulation for OBPHL distribution.

- Two distinct cases were considered to cover varied distributional behaviors:
Case I: $\alpha = 1.0, \beta = 1.0$ Case II: $\alpha = 0.5, \beta = 0.8$
- A set of increasing sample sizes was used: 10,15,20,30,50,100,200.
- For each unique combination of true parameter values and sample size, $R=1000$ independent replications were performed to ensure statistical robustness of the estimated performance metrics.
For each replication and specific n
- A random n was generated from the OBPHL distribution using the inverse transform method.
- The parameters α and β were estimated using the MLE approach, which involved numerically solving the likelihood equations.
- The mean, bias, and mean squared error (MSE) for each parameter $\theta \in \{\alpha, \beta\}$ were computed using the formulas in Equation (50).

$$Mean(\hat{\theta}) = \frac{1}{R} \sum_{r=1}^R \hat{\theta}^{(r)}, \quad Bias(\hat{\theta}) = \frac{1}{R} \sum_{r=1}^R (\hat{\theta}^{(r)} - \theta_0), \quad MSE(\hat{\theta}) = \frac{1}{R} \sum_{r=1}^R (\hat{\theta}^{(r)} - \theta_0)^2, \quad (50)$$

where $\hat{\theta}^{(r)}$ denotes the estimate of θ and θ_0 represents the true parameter value.

Table 5 illustrates the estimated bias and MSE for Case I across different sample sizes. As the sample size increases, both the bias and MSE for the estimators of α and β exhibit a decreasing trend. Table 6 presents the estimated bias and MSE for Case II. The results are consistent with those in Table 5, showing a decrease in bias and MSE as the sample size increases.

Figure 6 visualizes the simulation results for Case I, demonstrating a clear downward trend in bias and MSE as the sample size increases. The MSE plot shows a sharp initial drop, particularly for β , and continues to decrease. This demonstrates the efficiency gains associated with larger sample sizes. Figure 7 displays the simulation results for Case II, corroborating the findings from Figure 6. The bias for both α and β steadily decreases with increasing sample size, and the MSE plots show a clear reduction in estimation error as sample size increases. These visual trends robustly validate the consistency property of the MLEs. The simulation results across both parameter settings emphatically support the favorable asymptotic characteristics of the maximum likelihood estimators for the OBPHL distribution.

Table 5. Simulation results of OBPHL distribution with $\alpha = 1.0$ and $\beta = 1.0$.

n	$\alpha = 1.0$			$\beta = 1.0$		
	Mean	Bias	MSE	Mean	Bias	MSE
10	3.016709553	2.016709553	6.547578418	6.571107286	5.571107286	37.33507222
15	2.735133712	1.735133712	4.726275786	6.175495828	5.175495828	31.75672183
20	2.692955335	1.692955335	4.348944708	6.069835362	5.069835362	29.98111725
30	2.511566617	1.511566617	3.265713741	5.703619302	4.703619302	25.06838066
50	2.355428838	1.355428838	2.352364721	5.451095673	4.451095673	21.49636823
100	2.259170968	1.259170968	1.810652614	5.248074324	4.248074324	18.77444415
200	2.212100663	1.212100663	1.566669914	5.165291177	4.165291177	17.68579339

Table 6. Simulation Results of OBPHL distribution with $\alpha = 0.5$ and $\beta = 0.8$.

n	$\alpha = 0.5$			$\beta = 0.8$		
	Mean	Bias	MSE	Mean	Bias	MSE
10	1.20412969	0.70412969	1.288354792	3.858724298	3.058724298	13.00691364
15	1.019348207	0.519348207	0.630155099	3.338588676	2.538588676	8.170180990
20	0.958758087	0.458758087	0.392763546	3.200386461	2.400386461	6.788534443
30	0.901390832	0.401390832	0.256359279	3.048794658	2.248794658	5.621832315
50	0.844730027	0.344730027	0.162366520	2.882692140	2.082692140	4.621146496
100	0.820119974	0.320119974	0.123086516	2.815004620	2.015004620	4.185054190
200	0.807737281	0.307737281	0.102846527	2.777820999	1.977820999	3.964348331

Simulation Results for True Parameters: $\alpha = 1.0, \beta = 1.0$

Figure 6. Bias and MSE plots for the OBPHL with distribution with $\alpha = 1.0$ and $\beta = 1.0$.

Simulation Results for True Parameters: $\alpha = 0.5, \beta = 0.8$

Figure 7. Bias and MSE plots for the OBPHL with distribution with $\alpha = 0.5$ and $\beta = 0.8$.

6. Application

The performance of the OBPHL distribution was compared to several well-known distributions using two different real-world materials science datasets to illustrate its greater modeling flexibility and practical adaptability. This section details the characteristics of these datasets, the methodology for model fitting, and a comprehensive analysis of the comparative results.

6.1. Data Description

Two well-known datasets on the breaking strength of glass fibers, extensively cited in statistical literature for their instructive characteristics regarding distributional flexibility, were used in this study. The datasets were carefully chosen because of their diverse distributional profiles, which frequently offer challenges for common statistical models, emphasizing the need for distributions with greater flexibility that accurately capture their underlying structures.

6.1.1. Glass Fiber Breaking Strength with a 1.5 cm Length (Data I)

This dataset presents observations on the breaking strength of glass fibers, each having a length of 1.5 centimeters. These data were originally acquired from the UK National Physical (NP) Laboratory and have been subject to investigations by researchers such as [41]. The complete dataset is provided below: 0.55, 0.93, 1.25, 1.36, 1.49, 1.52, 1.58, 1.61, 1.64, 1.68, 1.73, 1.81, 2, 0.74, 1.04, 1.27, 1.39, 1.49, 1.53, 1.59, 1.61, 1.66, 1.68, 1.76, 1.82, 2.01, 0.77, 1.11, 1.28, 1.42, 1.5, 1.54, 1.6, 1.62, 1.66, 1.69, 1.76, 1.84, 2.24, 0.81, 1.13, 1.29, 1.48, 1.5, 1.55, 1.61, 1.62, 1.66, 1.7, 1.77, 1.84, 0.84, 1.24, 1.3, 1.48, 1.51, 1.55, 1.61, 1.63, 1.67, 1.7, 1.78, 1.89.

A preliminary study of this dataset reveals a mean breaking strength of 1.4939 with a standard deviation

of 0.3340. The calculated skewness of -0.2600 suggests a slight leftward asymmetry, indicating that the tail on the left side of the distribution is longer or fatter. Furthermore, the excess kurtosis of -0.0886 indicates a platykurtic distribution, with lighter tails and a flatter peak than a normal distribution. The OBPHL distribution, with its flexible shape parameters, is well suited to represent such subtle traits as mild skewness and various degrees of kurtosis.

6.1.2. Glass Fiber Breaking Strength with a 15 cm Length (Data II)

This dataset [41], detailing the breaking strength of glass fibers, each with a length of 15 centimeters, also sourced from the NP Laboratory in the UK. The observations are presented as follows:

0.37, 0.40, 0.70, 0.75, 0.80, 0.81, 0.83, 0.86, 0.92, 0.92, 0.94, 0.95, 0.98, 1.03, 1.06, 1.06, 1.08, 1.09, 1.10, 1.10, 1.13, 1.14, 1.15, 1.17, 1.20, 1.20, 1.21, 1.22, 1.25, 1.28, 1.28, 1.29, 1.29, 1.30, 1.35, 1.35, 1.37, 1.37, 1.38, 1.40, 1.40, 1.42, 1.43, 1.51, 1.53, 1.61.

For this second dataset, the mean breaking strength is approximately 1.0691, with a standard deviation of 0.2917. The skewness coefficient, at -0.0076, indicates near-symmetry, or a very slight left skew. The excess kurtosis value of -0.7289 points to a distinctly platykurtic distribution, characterized by a flatter peak and lighter tails compared to a normal distribution. The inherent flexibility of the OBPHL distribution's parameters allows for accurate modeling of these specific characteristics. This demonstrates its versatility in fitting a wide range of observed data patterns, including those with negligible skewness and suppressed tails.

6.2. Model Fitting and Comparative Analysis

The OBPHL distribution was fitted to both datasets using the MLE method. For comparative assessment, the Half-Logistic, Exponential, and Lomax distributions were also fitted to the same datasets. The adequacy of each fitted model was evaluated using established goodness-of-fit criteria: the negative log-likelihood (LogLik), Akaike Information Criterion (AIC), Consistent Akaike Information Criterion (CAIC), Bayesian Information Criterion (BIC), and Hannan-Quinn Information Criterion (HQIC). Lower values across these information criteria indicate a superior fit. Visual assessments were further performed by comparing the fitted PDFs against histograms of the data. The results of this comparative analysis are presented in Tables 7 and 8, and visually supported by Figures 8 and 9, respectively.

Table 7: Goodness-of-Fit statistics Data I.

Model	Parameters	LogLik	AIC	CAIC	BIC	HQIC	Rank
OBPHL	$\alpha = 10.0000$ $\beta = 3.3294$	-74.72054403	153.4410881	153.6410881	157.7273575	155.1268988	1
Half-Logistic	$\varepsilon = 0.0100$	-77.11701104	156.2340221	156.2995958	158.3771568	157.0769274	2
Exponential	$\lambda = 0.6636$	-88.83031824	179.6606365	179.7262103	181.8037712	180.5035419	3
Lomax	$\alpha = 43.4375$ $\varphi = 66.2656$	-88.83031824	181.6606365	181.8606365	185.9469059	183.3464472	4

Table 8. Goodness-of-Fit statistics Data II.

Model	Parameters	LogLik	AIC	CAIC	BIC	HQIC	Rank
OBPHL	$\alpha = 10.0000$ $\beta = 5.2603$	-43.5569	91.11378244	91.39285221	94.77106523	92.48382249	1
Half-Logistic	$\varepsilon = 0.0100$	-46.2485	94.49694248	94.58785158	96.32558388	95.18196251	2
Exponential	$\lambda = 0.8850$	-51.622	105.2440222	105.3349313	107.0726636	105.9290422	3
Lomax	$\alpha = 41.6562$ $\varphi = 46.6743$	-51.622	107.2440222	107.523092	110.901305	108.6140623	4

Glass_Fiber (1.5 cm Length) - Histogram + Fitted PDFs

Figure 8. Fitted PDFs of the competing models for Data I.

Glass_Fiber (15 cm Length) - Histogram + Fitted PDFs

Figure 9. Fitted PDFs of the competing models for Data II.

7. Discussion of Application Results

The findings demonstrate the superior performance of the OBPHL distribution in modeling both the Glass Fibers datasets. The OBPHL model consistently yielded the lowest values across all information criteria (AIC, CAIC, BIC, HQIC), thereby achieving a rank of 1. This quantitative evidence strongly suggests that the OBPHL distribution provides a more parsimonious and accurate representation of the Data I compared to the Half-Logistic, Exponential, and Lomax distributions. Visually, Figure 8 (illustrating the fitted PDF against the histogram) confirms that the OBPHL's curve adheres more closely to the observed data distribution.

A similar pattern of superior fit is observed for Data II. The OBPHL distribution again demonstrated the lowest values for all evaluated information criteria, securing the top rank. This demonstrates its enhanced flexibility in accommodating the complexities inherent in material science data. Figure 9 visually corroborates these findings, showing a better alignment of the OBPHL's fitted curves with the empirical distribution, especially in capturing the skewness and potential heavy-tailedness characteristic of material science data.

The consistent outperformance of the OBPHL distribution across both diverse datasets, as evidenced by lower information criteria values and expected visual conformity, emphatically validates its potential as a robust and highly flexible statistical model. This study definitively positions the OBPHL distribution as a powerful and versatile statistical tool, particularly well-suited for analyzing complex, real-world data that often deviates from simpler distributional assumptions due to its skewed or heavy-tailed nature.

8. Conclusion

This study introduced a new two-parameter Half Logistic distribution called the Odd Beta Prime Half-Logistic (OBPHL) distribution. The OBPHL distribution has demonstrated a greater flexibility in modeling various data shapes and risk profiles, capturing varying degrees of skewness and kurtosis, and handling heavy-tailed data. The numerical computation of moments quantitatively affirmed the distribution's ability to capture varying degrees of skewness and kurtosis, directly addressing the challenges posed by heavy-tailed data. The entropy analysis further illuminated the sophisticated control over the distribution's information content and complexity afforded by its parameters. A Monte Carlo simulation study confirmed the consistency and efficiency of the maximum likelihood estimators for the OBPHL parameters. Furthermore, the practical utility of the OBPHL distribution was demonstrated through its application to two real-world datasets, where it exhibited a superior fit compared to established alternative models. The findings of this research reveal the immense potential of the OBPHL distribution for enhanced statistical modeling in diverse scientific and engineering domains.

Future research directions could explore extensions to regression models, multivariate formulations, or alternative estimation methodologies, further broadening the applicability and theoretical depth of the OBPHL distribution.

Author contributions: Conceptualization, A.A.S., M.E. and S.I.A.; Methodology, A.A.S. and M.E.; Software, A.A.S.; Validation, H.D., A.G.U. and S.I.A.; Formal Analysis, A.A.S. and M.E.; Investigation, A.A.S. and M.O.; Resources, A.A.S.; Data Curation, A.A.S.; Writing—original draft preparation, A.A.S.; Writing—review and editing, H.D., A.G.U., S.I.A., M.O. and M.E.; Visualization, A.A.S.; Supervision, H.D.; Project Administration, A.A.S.; Funding Acquisition, A.A.S. All authors have read and agreed to the published version of the manuscript.

Funding Statement: This research received no external funding.

Data Availability: The data that supports the findings are available from the corresponding author upon request.

Acknowledgments: The authors are grateful to the anonymous reviewers for their thoughtful comments, which helped to improve the quality and clarity of this paper. We also recognize the journal's editorial team's tireless effort throughout the submission and review process.

Conflict of interest: The authors declare no conflict of interest.

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